

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF INFOGRAPHICS

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Abstract: *This article describes the importance of infographics today and its types. In addition, the advantages and disadvantages of infographics are analyzed.*

Key words: *infographics, information, advertising, educational materials, competence approach, modernization.*

The development trends of computer science education in the world (humanization, humanitarianization, technologicalization) show that modern forms and technologies of education are rapidly developing on national, regional and global scales. In particular, in European countries and the USA "Merit" (selecting gifted children for high school), VISBI (cooperation in education), Hed start (compensatory training aimed at academic mastery), PISA (international assessment of students)) programs, Dalton-plan (individual training system) are widely used. In the process of developing students' intellectual abilities, the use of modernized infographic tools based on the competency approach is gaining urgent importance.

Today, the demand and attention for graphic media products is increasing day by day. As the development of social media marketing develops, it is more effective to provide people with visual content - infographics instead of lengthy textual information about services, products and activities.

Infographics are a great way to present information. Especially for modern users who do not want to spend their time reading uncomfortable texts, but the graphic environment is well received. Saving students time and effort - all this can be achieved with infographics[1]. In which program we can do this. Infographics are easy and quick to adopt, easy to share, easy to do. In addition, according to statistics, information in the form of data is more informative. A nice bonus is that it's not too

difficult to create an infographic. If desired, it can be mastered at a critical time. Infographics is a graphical way of presenting information. In other words, it can be called image data. Infographics can include other elements (text, indicators, charts, blocks, and icons) where graphics play a key role.

Infographics, in general, are an independent means of information transfer. In short, infographics are designed to present material quickly, visually, and vividly[2].

There are five main types of infographics:

Analytical or digital infographics. With its help, statistical information is presented, which can contain a lot of numbers, charts, graphs.

News infographic. It tells a clear story about the latest events, reflects the chronology and the important stages of the events that are happening around.

Construction infographics. Shows the structure of an object or its mechanism, sometimes the chronology and causes of a historical event.

Advertising infographic. Created by companies to promote their products. As a rule, this can be a vivid picture describing the benefits of the product and the purchase[3]. If it's well-crafted, it can attract customers—that is, it combines competent marketing and good design.

Comparative infographic. Allows you to compare the properties of different objects.

Advantages of infographics:

First, infographics allow you to display large amounts of information—today's audience lacks the patience and time to read long stretches of text.

Second, a good infographic makes information clearer.

Third, an interesting image helps to attract the attention of the audience, so this format is widely used. In today's modern education system, it is recommended to use infographic materials more.

Disadvantages of infographics

- The first disadvantage of infographics is that it is not easy and cheap to make.

Writing a text or list is usually much easier, cheaper and faster than choosing the

right images and judiciously combining them[4]. In addition, to create a good infographic, you need creativity, creative design thinking.

- The second disadvantage is that sometimes such a colorful way of presenting the material can cause people to take this information less seriously.
- The third drawback is that infographics are almost always some kind of schematic, generalization and simplification of reality.
- The fourth minus depends more on the performers than on the method of presenting the information. The fact is that if a good infographic helps to absorb information, a bad one, on the contrary, hinders its perception and can even give the wrong explanation.

Using infographic elements in education:

- Infographics help to develop and form imagination in vocational education;
- Increases the level of visibility of the educational process;
- It helps to increase the mastery level by visualizing the educational process;
- By reflecting the social portrait of the profession, it motivates the learner to study the profession;
- By building a socio-economic portrait of the profession, it encourages the learner to gain confidence in the future and to build long-term plans for reaching the highest heights of the profession;
- To fully convey information about the position of the profession in the training of junior specialists to the learner;
- Infographics provide an opportunity to deepen the idea of national independence in the educational process.

Infographics are used almost everywhere. For example, in the media: but the first infographic was used only to present statistics.

- With the help of infographics, you can familiarize yourself with the information of customers or employees;
- You can show important news;
- Advertise your products and services;

- You will have prepared a user-friendly technical manual that is understandable to everyone, regardless of the language they speak;
- You can prepare statistical data, annual report, research results;

Infographics are widely used by entertainment and popular science sites - often to explain a device or mechanism. It is used in educational materials for the same purpose.

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